

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE IMPACT OF IMPURITIES ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF RECYCLED PVC EXTRUSION PIPES

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ABSTRACT

This work studied the effect of using recycled scraps in the production of rigid PVC extrusion pipe. Different formulations with varied percentages of scraps were extruded and various tests carried out on the sample specimen to determine their corresponding mechanical properties. It was finally discovered that among the two sources of scraps, the in-house scraps contained less impurities and blending about 10% of it with virgin PVC material in the production gave improved mechanical properties. The second type of scrap, 'post consumer used scraps' were found to have higher percentages of impurities. This and other factors including continuous re-extrusion, ageing, degradation and poor formulation from its origin affected the properties.

SIGNIFICANCE:

The study of the effects of using recycled materials provides valuable information to the industrialist producing PVC pipes in the country. If the use is found satisfactory it will reduce environmental pollution, benefit manufacturers of these products and employment opportunities will be provided in the ploughing back of waste to wealth.

KEYWORDS: Polyvinyl Chloride, Thermal Insulator, Extrusion, Die, Extruder, Archimedean Screw, Clearance, Solid Polymer, Exudates, Homogenize, Recycling, Tensile strength.

INTRODUCTION

Companies manufacturing PVC extrusion pipes have greatly embarked on using recycled materials (scraps) whether as 100% or as fraction of the virgin material in order to save material cost in an attempt to maximize profit. This has greatly introduced impurities into the production. The impurities have as well greatly affected the service properties of the produced pipes. (Morton, 1993)

This research, therefore attempted to provide useful information on the mechanical properties of those pipes produced from recycled PVC material and to come up with an illustration as to what extent and in what form has the impurities affected the extruded products service properties.

The work is restricted to the study of the mechanical properties of some samples of PVC pipes extruded from 100% virgin materials and that produced with PVC scraps. Various laboratory tests were carried out on samples and inference made based on the end results.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although this may be the first work involved with the investigation of the effects of impurities on the mechanical properties of PVC extrusion pipes, a lot of work was done in general on extrusion of PVC pipes, processes and machines, and recycling of PVC scraps.

In principle, the extrusion process comprises the forcing of a plastic or molten material through a shaped die by means of pressure. The process has been used for many years for metals such as aluminum that flow plastically under deforming pressure and in the earliest form of extrusion process for polymers similar ram-driven

machines were used. In the modern process, however, screws are used to progress the polymer in the molten or rubbery state along the barrel of the machine. The most widely used type is the single screw and twin screw extruder machines. The machines consist essentially of an Archimedean screw fitting closely in a cylindrical barrel, with just sufficient clearance to allow its rotation. Solid polymer is feed in at one and the profiled molten extrudate emerges from the other end, inside, the polymers melts and homogenizes. (Elsevier, 1985)

Extrusion of PVC pipes

Commercial extrusion encompass a wide variety of products, with sheet, film, extrusion coatings, pipe profiles, wire coatings, cable coatings, and blow mouldings as the most significant uses. From this listing, it is apparent that any operation in which a continuous form or shape is desired readily lends itself to extrusion. The final product is dependent on the die and the associated downstream equipment, but the vehicle for presenting the polymer to the die in the desired state is referred to as the extruder machine.

Single screw machines are in the most widespread use because of their adaptability to virtually all extrusion forms, and their inherent simplicity, which reflects itself in the ultimate cost. Twin-screw units, which are more complex in nature, are widely used in processing rigid PVC pipes and profiles, and in compounding because of their lower operating temperatures. This provides an end product with less heat history and which is less susceptible to degradation than an equivalent made on a single-screw extruder.

Features of a single-screw extruder.

The screw of an extruder has one or two 'flights' spirally along its length. The diameter to the outside of the flights is constant along the length to allow the close fit in the barrel. The 'root' or 'core' however is of varying diameter and so the spiraling channel depth decreases. In general, the channel depth decreases from feed end to the die end although there are variants for special purpose.

A consequence of the decreasing channel depth is increasing pressure along the extruder and this is what drives the melt through the die. There are also the die zones, which will be examined separately.

In analyzing a single screw-extruder there are essentially four key elements: the drive train, barrel, screw and die head.

Recycling Of Extruded Products

At the most basic level, the principles of reducing the impact of any process or product consists of avoiding waste, recovering waste and recycling waste. In the current competitive marketplace, every industry sector is aware of the need to avoid and recover waste where possible. The PVC industry is not alone in this but it is in front in term of recycling waste to minimize environmental impact.

All thermoplastics are by their very nature recyclable and can be reprocessed in a variety of ways including; Direct product re-use, Mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, In house recycling, Fabricator recycling, Post consumer used recycling and municipal solid waste recycling.(Elsevier, 1985)

METHODOLOGY

PVC 100% virgin materials was used to extrude some lengths of pipe under the normal setting of the extrusion machine. Some PVC pipes were produced as well from PVC material mixed with recycled material. Right from the production stage, the machine parameters were investigated to see changes that may occur which could in turn have effect on the properties of the extruding pipes.

Laboratory tests were also carried out in both cases (with and without recycled material) in Panar Nigeria Limited, Sharada, Kano, Nigeria, one of the PVC extrusion pipe producing company.

Each of the produced samples was used for the determination of the following mechanical properties.

- Impact strength at 27°C
- Impact strength at 0°C

- Hydrostatic properties
- Tensile properties.
- Flattening properties.

The results of the above tests were compared with Nigeria Industrial Standards (NIS 76, 1980) recommendation for rigid PVC pipes and the suitability of using the recycled material in the production of

PVC extrusion pipes was ascertained.

Formulation

PVC resin alone cannot be used directly to produce pipes, there are additives to make up the formulation. These were mixed thoroughly in both hot cold mixers before being discharged for extrusion. In the experiments, different formulations were attempted in extruding different pipes and the corresponding tests carried out accordingly. The table below gives the different formulations attempted.

Table-1: Different Formulations Attempted

Sample	A	B	C	D
Virgin PVC (kg)	100	100	100	100
Filler (CaCO ₃) kg	15.0	15.0	15.0	15.0
Stabilizer (PbSO ₄) (kg)	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2
Stearic acid (kg)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
PVC-scrap (kg)	Nil	10.0	20.0	30.0
Carbon-black (kg)	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03

Mixing process

The mixing machine comprises of the hot and cold mixing chambers. Each formation was put into the hot chamber (except the recycled scraps), heated to a temperature of 110°C and continuously stirred until a homogenous mixture was obtained.

It was discharged into the cold chamber and cooled at a temperature of 35°C. At this stage, the recycled scrap was added, stirred thoroughly and discharged into barrels for extrusion.

Extrusion Procedure

The extruder machine used for the experiments has the following parameters.

Name: Klockner Windsor Machine

Type: Twin Screw Extruder

Model: Kts-120

Output: Maximum Output-120kg/Hr

Torque: 130kgm Maximum

Speed: 4rpm-40rpm

Screw Dia: 65mm

Machine parameter set-up

The extruder machine temperatures were set and left for two hours before production commenced. After successfully heating of the machine, the production was carried out using the different formulation stated above. For the production of all the samples, the extruder was run at 40 rpm with a torque of 90kgm.

Laboratory Tests

Laboratory tests were conducted in order to determine and compare the mechanical properties of the various pipes extruded from the various formulations. The pipe size extruded and used for all the experiments was having outside diameter of 110mm and wall thickness of 3.2mm.

The first step before conducting the experiment consists of preparation of the sample specimen. Each of the specimens was a complete section of pipe, cut to a length of 300mm. The end of the specimen was cut cleaned and squared to the axis of the pipe.

Two cases were considered in all the experimental analysis carried out.

CASE 1: Post-consumer used scraps (i.e. external scraps).

CASE 2: In-house scraps (i.e. internal scraps).

Experiment 1: Test for Impact Strength at 27°C.

Aim: The aim of this experiment was to determine the impact strength of the different extruded pipes at 27°C.

TABLE 1: Results of the Experiments and NIS Recommendation

	N I S	VIRGIN	C A S E -1			C A S E -2			
TESTS		A	B	C	D	B	C	D	
Impact strength at 27 °C (strikes)	12/14 14/14	-	14/14	7/14	0/14	0/14	14/14	13/14	8/14
Impact strength at 0 °C (strikes)	13/14 14/14	-	13/14	1/14	0/14	0/14	14/14	12/14	5/14
Hydrostatic Property (22 bar)	1hr		1hr	1hr	21min	11min	1hr	1hr	1hr
Tensile strength at break (MN/m ²)	42.2		46.9	27.3	15.6	15.6	46.9	39.1	39.1
Elongation at break (%)	80		79.6	1.14	0.43	0.23	71.4	53.5	22.7
Tensile modulus (N/mm)	-		517.86	1062.5	1250	2580	1128.21	1738.10	2433.33
Toughness (J)	-		342.2	58.7	16.0	8.0	123.2	68.6	49.0
Flattening	Passed		Passed	Failed	Failed	Failed	Passed	Passed	Passed

Apparatus: The apparatus comprises of a falling weight machine, guide rails, a specimen support comprising 120° Vee block of 230mm in length, meter rule, micrometer screw gauge (accuracy=0.01mm), and vernier calliper of accuracy 0.02mm.

For pipe size 110mm x 3.2mm, NIS recommended that:

Weight of striker = 2.75kg

Height of fall = 2m (NIS, 76, 1980)

Procedure:

Each specimen was marked with a longitudinal zero line positioned at random with a marker pen, and from this line, further four parallel lines were marked equidistantly on the specimen. The pipe was placed on the Vee block so that one of the marked lines is uppermost. .

A weighted striker of mass 2.75kg was allowed to fall freely through a height of 2m on to the marked line on the pipe specimen centrally mounted on the Vee block support.

If the specimen did not fail as a result of cracking or splitting, it is rotated until the next marked line is uppermost in the Vee block, and a second blow made by the striker. The process was repeated until all the marked lines were tested or until a failure was recorded.

Experiment 2: Test for Impact Strength at 0°C

Aim: The aim of this experiment was to compare the impact strength of the different formulated extruded pipe at 0°C.

Apparatus: The apparatus is the same as for test 1 stated above.

Procedure: The mass of the striker and height of free fall were adjusted to the values appropriate to the diameter of the test piece.

Mass of striker used = 0.5kg,
Height of free fall = 2.0m

The tests procedure was the same as for test 1, only that each specimen was conditioned in a refrigerator at a temperature of 0°C for 1 hour prior to the test.

Experiment 3: Hydrostatic Test

Aim: The aim of this test was to compare the short-term hydrostatic property for the sample specimen.

Apparatus: The apparatus consists of a bath of water maintained at 27°C and the equipment permits the application of a controlled internal hydrostatic pressure to the specimen to an accuracy of +/- 2%.

- Spanners for tightening the bolts and nuts.
- File for chamfering the pipe edges for easy coupling of the clamps.

Procedure: 600mm length of each specimen was cut, with the edges cut smooth and chamfered, the pressure clamps were fixed at both ends of the specimen, water was pumped into the pipe to fill it and pressure applied. The amount of pressure applied was governed by the formula. (Nielsen, 1992)

$$P = \frac{2 \cdot \delta \cdot t}{d_m}$$

Where δ = induced or hoop stress of PVC (in bars)
T = minimum wall thickness of the pipe (mm)

P = internal pressure (bar)
 d_m = mean outside diameter of the pipe

Therefore

δ = 361.2 bar for rigid PVC

t = 3.2mm

d_m = 110.2mm

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \frac{2 \times 361.2}{110.2 - 3.2} \\ &= \frac{2311.6}{107} \\ &= 21.6 \text{ bar} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore 22bar pressure will be applied.

The specimen mounted on the apparatus and the calculated internal pressure of 22bar applied and maintained throughout the test period of 1 hour.

Results: After 1 hour of pressure application to each sample, observations were made and recorded.

Experiment 4: Test for Tensile Properties

Aim: The aim of this experiment is to determine and compare various tensile properties like tensile modulus, tensile strength, toughness and elongation of the produced specimen.

Apparatus: The tensile tester machine used for the experiment was having the following details.

Name: Oswaldo Filizola Tensile Tester

Model No: 5504

Maximum Capacity: 1000kg

Accuracy: 10kg

It comprises of the following major components.

- A fixed part which supports a clamping device
- A moveable part supporting the second clapping device
- Micrometer screw gauge with an accuracy of 0.01mm for measuring the width and thickness of the specimen.
- Digital vernier caliper for measuring distance (length) of the specimen with an accuracy of 0.02mm.

Procedure: A sample of 750mm long was taken at a time; it was cut open along a plane through the axis. The specimen was heated in a thermally regulated oven at a temperature of 130°C for 7 minutes. At the end of the heating period, the piece of pipe was taken from the oven and placed immediately between two metal plates at ambient temperature; sufficient pressure was applied for flattening without bringing about any perceptible variation in the initial thickness. Then a 15mm wide bar was cut from the plate obtained in the direction corresponding with the longitudinal direction of the pipe.

Each specimen was conditioned at 27°C for 1 hour immediately before testing. Both end of each test piece hold on to the devices of the tensile testing machine, load was applied on it and the corresponding length of the calibrated part of the specimen was read and recorded.

From the results the followings were deduced

1. Tensile strength at brake
2. Percentage elongation
3. Tensile modulus
4. Toughness

The results were summarized as shown in the table 1.

Experiment 5: Test for Flattening Properties

Aim: The aim of this experiment was to compare the flattening properties of the extruded different formulation.

Apparatus: Hack saw, table vice

Procedure: A ring-shape test piece 50mm long of each sample was cut and conditioned at 27 °C for one hour. The each test piece was flattened diametrically in a parallel plate of the vice until the distance between the plates was equal to 44mm (40% of the outside diameter of the test specimen) the rate of loading was uniform and the compression was completed within 5 minutes.

On removal of the load, each test piece was examined for evidence of splitting, cracking, or breaking.

RESULTS

All the tests performed under this section were carried out in the Laboratory Department of Panar Nigeria Ltd. A PVC pipes manufacturing company located at Sharada Industrial Estate, Phase II, Kano, Nigeria. The results of the various experiments and the N.I.S values are shown in Table 1.

DISCUSSION

Table 2 below summarized and compares the Nigeria Industrial Standard (NIS) requirements for rigid PVC pipe production and the test results of all the experiments carried out.

From table 2, one can see that all the samples made From external scraps has a property below NIS standard (case 1-B, C, D), while under case 2 (B, C, D) the properties of the tests samples varied, but above all, sample B (made from 10% internal scrap) compete with sample A (made from 100% virgin) in all the properties.

The experiment has proved the theory that if in-house scrap (scrap free from impurities) is blended with virgin PVC material, it extend and sometimes improved the properties of the produced products', this experiment also shows that at least up to 10% of the recycled scraps can be blended with virgin PVC compound and used successfully for effective and improved mechanical properties including tensile strength, impact strength, & tensile modulus.

CONCLUSION

This work has studied several cases of production formulations for extrusion pipes and all the necessary mechanical properties tested in accordance with NIS test procedure. From the experimental analysis, internal scraps of up to 10% of the virgin PVC compound is safe for use as it doesn't set-back the properties of the products but that it can even boost some properties such as impact strength, tensile modulus etc.

Industrialists are hereby discouraged from using externally sourced PVC scraps. This work has proved that this source of the material severely affect the mechanical properties of the extruded product, respective of proportions used. This is due to the fact that the scraps might have undergone ageing, continuous re-extrusion, degradation, or poor formulation from its origin. It might have also been affected by UV-light or it may contain high degree of impurities. (Nazdaneh, 2000, Sombatsompop and Sungsanit, 2003, Salihu, 1998)

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